

GENDER ROLES IN AGRICULTURAL DECISION-MAKING AMONG FARMING HOUSEHOLDS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS**Aristeo C. Salapa****ORCID ID - 0000-0003-0934-3571**

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the impact of gender on decision-making in agriculture based on a PRISMA 2020-guided systematic review of published literature. The study focused on empirical studies published between 2018 and 2024 that concerned the role of gender in crop selection, labor division, and resource allocation in developing and emerging countries. 100 records were searched across multiple academic databases, of which six empirical studies met the criteria. Findings show that gender differentials still exist in decision-making, with men usually having the final authority to decide and take control of agricultural strategies, while women, on the other hand, remain responsible for labor-intensive and unpaid household tasks. The existence of joint decision-making has been documented; yet, imbalances persist, limiting women's influence in accessing various allocations and opportunities. The review emphasizes the importance of enhancing women's gender-responsive policies in agriculture, as well as interventions that empower and enhance women's decision-making capabilities to improve household productivity and achieve sustainability.

Keywords:

Gender roles, Farming households, Decision-making, Crop selection, Division of labor, PRISMA

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture remains a cornerstone and the backbone of the Philippine economy, playing a crucial role in the country's development and ensuring food security. The domination of males in the agricultural field leads to a poor recognition of women as farmers, and despite the long-standing issues with gender-mainstreaming programs and policies, including improving the participation of women, as they do not have sufficient representation in key decision-making bodies such as local government units (LGUs) and farmers' cooperative associations (FCAs) (Ani & Casasola, 2020).

Gender plays a significant role in shaping agricultural production, labor allocation within the household, and the decision-making process. Both men and women make significant contributions, but they differ in terms of access to agricultural resources such as crop selection, division of labor, and resource allocation. In rural communities, men and women participate in farming in many developing countries; however, their duties, responsibilities, and authority in decision-making, there is still little empirical evidence on how it directly influence gender roles in decision-making at the household level (Pelekamoyo & Umar, 2019).

Research on national and regional issues related to gender and agriculture has increased in the Philippines over the past decade (Dacuycuy, 2018). Despite identifying the constraints and contributions faced by both genders, analyzing gender roles is vital in agricultural decision-making to strengthen equitable engagement and enhance household resilience and agricultural productivity.

To understand these gendered tendencies, it is essential to encourage and promote equal participation in agricultural activities, thereby ensuring the resilience and productivity of smallholder households. Analyzing gender-based aspects in agricultural decision-making provides important insights into how they impact livelihood outcomes, shared responsibilities, and the distribution of authority, thereby informing the development of gender-responsive methods and promoting inclusivity.

Therefore, to address this gap, the research incorporates a systematic review that adheres to the PRISMA 2020 guidelines to examine gender roles and participation in agricultural decision-making, specifically in crop selection, labor division, and resource allocation. This approach yields a comprehensive understanding of how

the impact of gender roles shapes decision-making in farming households, providing substantial backing for evidence-based policy recommendations.

OBJECTIVES

The study aims to analyze the roles of gender and their influence on agricultural decision-making in farming households.

Specifically, it seeks to:

- 1) To identify the relationship between the gender roles of men and women in farming households
- 2) To assess how men and women participate in agricultural decision-making in terms of:
 - a. crop selection
 - b. division of labor
 - c. resource allocation
- 3) To compare the participation levels of men and women in agricultural decision-making and examine whether significant differences exist.
- 4) To determine how gender roles influence agricultural decision-making among farming households.

METHODOLOGY

The study adheres to the PRISMA-based systematic review research design to assess, evaluate, and identify existing empirical research on gender roles and agricultural decision-making in farming households. The four-stage review process, consisting of screening, identification, evaluation, and selection of eligible candidates, was guided by the PRISMA 2020 protocol to ensure a transparent approach and provide insights relevant to the study. (Page et al., 2021).

Eligibility Criteria

The study defines the exclusion and inclusion criteria to ensure the study focuses within its scope. Empirical studies that have been peer-reviewed and examined gender roles in agriculture, specifically those published between 2018 and 2024, were included. Additionally, the study focused on investigating decision-making in households, particularly in relation to crop selection, division of labor, and resource allocation. The next criterion of the study is that it should be conducted in the Philippines or in developing countries and emerging countries, and it should be written in English. The study also accepts relevant publications, peer-reviewed journal articles, theses, and studies that employed quantitative, qualitative, and mixed-method research designs. Databases included were utilized, including ScienceDirect, JSTOR, ResearchGate, Google Scholar, and Taylor & Francis. Excluded from the criteria were non-empirical works, such as opinionated pieces, commentaries, duplicates, and studies that could not be accessed in full text and were published prior to 2018. Studies conducted outside of agricultural or rural settings, as well as those not examining decision-making roles, are also excluded. While the number is limited, only six studies met all criteria. If the process of research is transparent and reproducible, the PRISMA allows systematic reviews with only a small dataset (Page et al., 2021).

Study Selection Process and Data Extraction

The retrieved records were imported, and all duplicate files have been removed. The screening process involved first screening by title and abstract, followed by an examination of the full text to filter out research that was not directly related to the study, such as studies on gender roles or agricultural decision-making in farming households. Additionally, articles that did not present empirical data on gender-related agricultural dynamics at this stage were excluded, in line with the Cochrane Handbook, a guidance document with consistent criteria that were filtered out during the early review process (Higgins et al., 2019).

To be included in the studies, an extraction process has been conducted, which includes the author(s), year of publication, study design, and the domains addressed in decision-making, as well as how these domains were operationalized or defined in relation to gender roles, and the relevant findings related to gender and decision-making.

Figure 1: The Systematic Review Process PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram based

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 presents the systematic review process based on the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram. The records identified through the database search were 100. These studies were outsourced through a careful selection and identification process. After the thorough process, duplicate records were removed, and 95 results were left. In the next step, 79 records were excluded, and 16 remained after screening. Out of 16 full-text articles that were assessed, there were 10 records excluded because they were either unrelated to agricultural decision-making at the household level, 4 were non-empirical, and 6 came from irrelevant outcomes and contexts. The final studies included in the qualitative synthesis comprise 6 empirical studies published between 2018 and 2024.

Study Characteristics

Author(s)	Year	Country	Study Design	Sample Size	Key findings
1. Acosta et al.	2020	Uganda, Ethiopia	Mixed method	210	Collaborative decision-making in households reveals how men often prevail in resource allocation and key crop decisions.
2. Ani & Casasola	2020	Philippines	Quantitative	150	Women have inadequate authority over resource allocation even if they participate in farm labor.
3. Carnegie et al.	2020	Myanmar	Action Research	180	Cultural norms continue to hinder the power of women, despite their increased participation in

					decision-making due to intervention.
4. Devkota et al.	2022	Nepal	Qualitative	75	Women are not appropriately represented in innovation ideas, and gender mainstreaming guidelines were applied unevenly.
5. Han et al.	2024	China	Quantitative	250	Household land leasing arrangements are impacted due to the gendered division of labor, and for the workload, women are predominantly responsible for it.
6. Msofi Mgalamadzi et al.	2024	Malawi	Quantitative	120	Despite the significant contribution to farm labor, women's decisions are limited to crops and household expenditure.

Thematic Synthesis of Findings

The study's findings were synthesized into three main topics related to gender roles in agricultural decision-making. These findings demonstrate how gender influences the outcomes and results in agricultural households, identifying recurring trends across various research techniques and national contexts.

Theme 1: Gendered Division of Decision-Making Power in Agricultural Households

Decision-making power in Agricultural Households along gender lines is still unequally distributed. Women were seen as more involved in labor allocation, post-harvest activities, and household management; on the other hand, men tended to dominate more in high-value decisions, such as financial investments, land use, and crop selection. Nevertheless, several studies show that decision-making is sometimes collaborative rather than individual, particularly in homes where women make a significant contribution to farm labor or income (Acosta et al., 2020; Carnegie et al., 2020; Msofi Mgalamadzi et al., 2024). The concept of "joint decision-making" also became complicated because males still maintain ultimate authority, even though women appear to participate.

Theme 2: Labor Allocation

Despite the interventions or any policies that increase the awareness of the role of women, they still bear the burden of being an unpaid farm laborer and performing domestic duties, resulting in limiting their time for capacity-building activities (Ani & Casasola, 2020; Han et al., 2024).

Theme 3: Access to Resources

Access to different agricultural resources, such as land, credit, and training for women, remains limited and restricted, which hinders their capabilities to engage in new innovations and adapt to new implementations of improvements in farm activity, reinforcing existing gaps in gender (Ani & Casasola, 2020; Devkota et al., 2022)

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CONCLUSION

The study, using the PRISMA 2020 framework, reviews various empirical evidence on gender roles in agricultural decision-making among farming households. The study's findings indicate that gender remains a crucial factor in determining participation, authority, and access to resources within the household. Women's involvement in strategic decision-making, particularly in crop selection and resource allocation, remains limited. The study further shows that women's decision-making power continues to remain constrained due to unequal access to assets and the lack of consistency in the implementation of gender mainstreaming policies, as well as cultural norms. Even though there are studies about the progress through interventions for some women, it still masks the persistent power that highly favors men.

These findings highlight the need for stronger agricultural policies that provide gender-responsive institutional support and capacity building, highly encouraging and recognizing women as key players in the field of agriculture, rather than merely being recognized as contributors to labor. To better understand how gender-inclusive decision-making can enhance resilience in the household, agricultural output, and sustainable rural development, future research with more empirical evidence should be expanded to investigate a wider range of contexts and explore more intervention-based approaches.

REFERENCES

- 1) Acosta, M., Van Wessel, M., Van Bommel, S., Ampaire, E. L., Twyman, J., Jassogne, L., & Feindt, P. H. (2020). What does it Mean to Make a 'Joint' Decision? Unpacking Intra-household Decision Making in Agriculture: Implications for Policy and Practice. *The Journal of Development Studies*, 56(6), 1210–1229. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220388.2019.1650169>
- 2) Ani, P. A. B., & Casasola, H. C. (2020, May 28). *Transcending Barriers in Agriculture through Gender and Development*. FFTC Agricultural Policy Platform (FFTC-AP). <https://ap.ffc.org.tw/article/1872>
- 3) Carnegie, M., Cornish, P. S., Htwe, K. K., & Htwe, N. N. (2020). Gender, decision-making and farm practice change: An action learning intervention in Myanmar. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 78, 503–515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2020.01.002>
- 4) Dacuycu, C. (2018). *Crafting Policies and Programs for Women in the Agriculture Sector*. Philippine Institute for Development Studies. <https://doi.org/10.62986/pn2018.08>
- 5) Devkota, R., Pant, L. P., Hambly Odame, H., Rai Paudyal, B., & Bronson, K. (2022). Rethinking gender mainstreaming in agricultural innovation policy in Nepal: A critical gender analysis. *Agriculture and Human Values*, 39(4), 1373–1390. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-022-10326-1>
- 6) Han, W., Zhang, Z., & Zhang, X. (2024). How does household farmland rental behavior affect gender differences in labor division and livelihood strategy? Insights from the household production theory. *Land Use Policy*, 147, 107362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2024.107362>
- 7) Higgins, J., Thomas, J., Chandler, J., Cumpston, M., Li, T., Page, M. J., Welch, V. A., & Cochrane Collaboration (Eds.). (2019). *Cochrane handbook for systematic reviews of interventions* (Second edition). Wiley Blackwell.
- 8) Huyer, S. (2016). Closing the Gender Gap in Agriculture. *Gender, Technology and Development*, 20(2), 105–116. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0971852416643872>
- 9) Msofi Mgalamadzi, L., Matita, M., & Chimombo, M. (2024). The gendered nature of household decision making and expenditure choices in the context of smallholder agricultural commercialization in Malawi. *CABI Agriculture and Bioscience*, 5(1), 65. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43170-024-00270-x>
- 10) Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *Systematic Reviews*, 10(1), 89. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-021-01626-4>
- 11) Pelekamoyo, J., & Umar, B. B. (2019). Access to and control over agricultural labor and income in smallholder farming households: A gendered look from Chipata, Eastern Zambia. *Journal of Gender, Agriculture and Food Security (Agri-Gender)*, 4, 42–57. <https://doi.org/10.19268/JGAFS.422019.4>